

ISSN 2181-0000
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0000

JOURNAL OF MAMUN SCIENCE

Volume 4, Issue 6 **2026**

ISSN 2181-0000
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0000

«MA'MUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

4 JILD, 6 SON

ЖУРНАЛ «MAMUN SCIENCE»

TOM 4, HOMEP 6

JOURNAL OF «MAMUN SCIENCE»

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 6

TOШKENT-2026

«MA'MUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

ЖУРНАЛ «МА'МUN SCIENCE» | JOURNAL OF «MAMUN SCIENCE»

№6 (2026) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0000-2026-6>

Бош мухаррир: | Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Matyakubov Umidjon Raximovich
(i.f.d., prof.)

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари: | Заместитель
главного редактора: | Deputy Chief Editor:

Xudonazarov Egambergan Madrahimovich
(PhD., dots.)

TAHRIRIY MASLAHAT KENGASHI | EDITORIAL BOARD | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

FILOLOGIYA FANLARI

O'rozboyev Abdulla Durdibayevich

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Axmedov Oybek Saporboyevich

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

Galiyeva Margarita Rafaelovna

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

Nasrullayeva Nafisa Zafarovna

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Samarqand davlat chet tillari instituti

Cho'ponov Otanazar Otojonovich

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc)

Urganch davlat universiteti

Yakubova Matluba Tajibayevna

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Matnazarov Javlanbek Kabulovich

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

TARIX FANLARI

Anatoliy Sagdullayevich Sagdullayev

Tarix fanlari doktori, professor; akademik

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar

akademiyasining haqiqiy a'zosi

Ashirov Adhamjon Azimbayevich

Tarix fanlari doktori, professor,

O'zbekiston Respublikasi

Fanlar akademiyasi Tarix instituti.

Shaydurov Vladimir Nikolayevich

Tarix fanlari doktori, dotsent

Leningrad davlat universiteti Rossiya

Abdullayev Utkir Ismoilovich

Tarix fanlari doktori (DSc),

dotsent Urganch davlat universiteti

Matkarimova Sadoqat Maqsudovna

Tarix fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Abdullayev Timur Pulatovich

Tarix fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Abdalov Umidbek Matniyazovich

Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD),

Dotsent Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Yunusxo'jayev Habibulla Zafar o'g'li

Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD),

Dotsent Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

PSIXOLOGIYA FANLARI

Shoumarov G'ayrat Baxromovich

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor; akademik

O'zbekiston Respublikasi

Fanlar akademiyasining haqiqiy a'zosi

Kryukova Tatyana Leonidovna

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor

Kostroma davlat universiteti Belorusiya

Karpinskiy Konstantin Viktorovich

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor

Grodno davlat universiteti Belorusiya

Urazbayeva Dilbar Abdullayevna

Psixologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Jumaniyazova Nasiba Ramatillayevna

Psixologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Nurullayeva Baxtigul Bobojonovna

Psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent Ma'mun

Universiteti NTM

IQTISODIYOT FANLARI

Ruzmetov Baxtiyar

Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Sherov Alisher Bakberganovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Voronsova Yuliya Vladimirovna

Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi

Moskva davlat boshqaruvi universiteti

Jabborov Umarbek Rustambekovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Cho'ponov San'at Otanazarovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Niyazmetov Islambek Masharipovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

PEDAGOGIKA VA FALSAFA FANLARI

Sardor Sharifzoda O'razboy Tabib o'g'li

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa
doktori (PhD), professor

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Adilov Zafar Yunusovich

Falsafa fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Boltayev Abdurahim Amanovich

Falsafa fanlari doktori, dotsent

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Zoirov Erkin Xalilovich

Falsafa fanlari doktori, dotsent

Buxoro davlat texnika universiteti

Nurullayeva Baxtigul Bobojonovna

Psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent Ma'mun

Universiteti NTM

TIBBIYOT FANLARI

Yuldashev Baxrom Sobirjanevich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Abdullayev Ravshanbek Babajonovich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Esamuratov Aybek Ibragimovich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Samandarova Barno Sultonovna

Biologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Tajiyeva Zebo Baxodirovna

Tibbiyot fanlari falsafa doktori (PhD)

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

ILMIY JURNAL TEXNIK KOTIBI

Yunusxo'jayev Habibulla Zafar o'g'li

Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Журнал включен в перечень ВАК национальных научных изданий, рекомендуемых для публикации основных научных результатов диссертаций по медицинским наукам постановлением № 01-08/3068/17 от 27 сентября 2024 г.

Page Maker | Верстка | Саифаловчи: X. Mirzaxmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

IQTSOD

1. Boltayev B. Mixliyev O.
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH SHAROITIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....7

2. Djumabayeva Sh.
O‘ZBEKISTONDA NIKOH VA AJRALISH JARAYONLARINING IJTIMOY-DEMOGRAFIK O‘ZGARISHLARI.....11

3. Raximov Matqurbon Ravshanbek O‘g‘li.
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIKNI TA‘MINLASHNING ZARURATI.....19

4. Rustamboyev Kamronbek Otabek o‘g‘li.
O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASH YO‘LLARI.....24

5. Курбанова Дилфуза Баходировна.
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И НАУЧНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ОТРАСЛЕЙ СФЕР УСЛУГ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ.....27

6. Egamberdiyev Shoxruxbek Davronbekovich.
KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATIGA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....33

FILOLOGIYA

1. Jo‘rayeva Muhayyo Abduljalilovna
O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ SO‘ZLASHUV DISKURSIDA DISKURS MARKERLARINING INTERAKTIV-PRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....38

2. Raximova Dilfuza Masharip qizi.
“XX–XXI ASR BRITANIYA ROMANLARIDA SHARQ VA G‘ARB BADIY TAFAKKURI SINTEZI”.....42

3. Baxtiyorov Asadbek Dilshod o‘g‘li.
ANTONIO JENKINSON VA UNING XIVA XONLIGIGA TASHRIFI.....46

4. Ювашева Шоира Махаматовна
ВЛИЯНИЕ КУЛЬТУРНЫХ НОРМ НА ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ ЛИЧНОСТИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ.....48

PSIXOLOGIYA

1. Mashhura Sultonova Rustamboyevna.
YETUKLIK YOSHIDAGI AYOLLARDA O‘Z-O‘ZIDAN QONIQISH DARAJASIGA PSIXOLOGIK RESURLAR VA QADRIYATLAR TIZIMINING TA‘SIRI.....52

2. Sherjanova Nodira.
MIGRANT OILALARDA TARBIIYALANAYOTGAN O‘SMIRLARDA PROSOTSIAL XULQ-ATVOR VA EMPATIYA MUNOSABATI.....58

3. Odamova O'g'iljon Kenjayevna. SHAXSLARARO MUNOSABATLARNING YUZAGA KELISH SABABLARI.....	63
--	----

TARIX

1. Egamberdieva Nigora Azadovna. Raxmatullaeva Azada. XORAZM VOHASIDA ILK DAVLATNING SHAKLANISHI JARAYONINING TAHLILI (ARXEOLOGIK VA YOZMA MANBALAR ASOSIDA).....	68
2. Abdullayev U.I. Kurshat Y. Satimov B. OROLBO'YIDA MUDOFA ISTEHKOMLARNING KELIB CHIQISHI BO'YICHA BA'ZI BIR MULOHAZALAR.....	73
3. Egamberdiyeva Zulfiya Zafar qizi. OLTIN O'RDA DAVRIDA XORAZMDA IQTISODIY HAYOT.....	78
4. Бобождонов У. ҚЎЙҚИРИЛГАН ҚАЛЪА АНТИК ДАВР МАДАНИЙ МЕРОС МАРКАЗИ.....	82
5. Umidbek Abdalov Matniyazovich. Ibodullayeva Oymarjon Shavkat qizi. FROM THE HISTORY OF DIPLOMATIC AND ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN THE KHIVA KHANATE AND THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE AT THE BEGINNING OF THE 18 th - 20 th CENTURIES.....	86

PEDAGOGIKA

1. Ismoilova Gulnoza Olimboy qizi. BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILARNING 4 K KOMPETENSIYALARINI RAQAMLI TA'LIM MUHITIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	91
2. Yunusxo'jayev Mustafo Zafarxo'ja o'g'li. NAJMIDDIN KUBRO PEDAGOGIK QARASHLARI ASOSIDA TALABALARNING MA'NAVIY-AXLOQIY KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK MODELI.....	96
3. Radjapova Feruza Abdullayevna. PEDAGOGIK MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DIDAKTIK TASNIFI VA ULARNI PEDAGOGIK TA'LIMGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH ALGORITMI...106	106

Umidbek Abdalov Matniyazovich.

Associate Professor of the Department of History, Mamun University,

Ibodullayeva Oymarjon Shavkat qizi.

History student at Mamun University,

**FROM THE HISTORY OF DIPLOMATIC AND ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN
THE KHIVA KHANATE AND THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE AT THE BEGINNING OF THE
18th - 20th CENTURIES**

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21008928>

Abstract: The article deals with diplomatic relations and economic problems between Russian empire and Khiva khanate in 18-20th centuries on the basis of foreign authors' works and archive documents. Some information about ambassadors of Russia and Khiva was given.

Key words: diplomatic mission, pood, rouble, Bekovich-Cherkasskiy, Nizhny Novgorod, contribution, act of obligations, Krasnavodsk, Manghishlak, emroli, yawmoot, chawdoor, Qabarda.

During the 16th century, the conquest of the Kazan, Astrakhan, and Siberian khanates by the Russian kingdom, and the conquest of small states belonging to the Kazakh tribes during the 17th century, caused Russia to become a border with Central Asia. This leads to the expansion of trade and diplomatic relations. The purpose of Russian penetration into the markets of Central Asia was to open new trade routes through this region to India and China. This can also be seen in the main verse of the instructions given by Peter I to Alexander Bekovich-Cherkassky, the leader of the military expedition sent to Khiva in 1717: "If the khan agrees, let 2 Russians be added to the khan's men and they should be sent to Yarkent to find out the presence of gold in Syr Darya. Also, ask the Khan to provide a ship for our merchants to go to India via Amu Darya. Let the merchants, when they depart, discover the land and water routes, especially the routes to India. If it is possible to go through the Caspian Sea, let them go back that way and write down what they saw" [1:30].

There are reasons for organizing this expedition. In 1713, the Turkmen merchant Khoja Nafas went to Astrakhan and met Prince Mikhail Samonov, who was the governor of Ghilan region in Iran, and who later came to Russia and converted to Christianity. Khoja Nafas told him that gold had been found in the area of the old valley of Amu Darya. Siberia, who went to St. Petersburg with this information

Governor of Sibiria Matvei Gagarin presented the gold to the Emperor which found in Syr Darya. For this reason, this military expedition was organized, and Iskandarbek (Alexandr Bekovich-Cherkassky), a Muslim by origin, was appointed as the leader of the expedition. The original homeland of this person was Qabarda (a region in the North Caucasus region). Later he married the daughter of the Russian prince Golitsyn and converted to Christianity. Later, he served in the regiment in Preobrazhensk with the rank of poruchik (junior officer in the army of the Russian Empire). But, this expedition ended in failure due to the trick of Khivan Khan [1:33].

However, earlier and later, some Khans of Khiva wrote letters asking for help from the Russian emperors in the struggle for the throne and even expressing their intention to become

Russian citizens. For example, Khan of Khiva Shahniyaz (1698-1702) wrote a letter of this content to Peter I in 1700. This proposal was later considered by Peter I and in 1703 he wrote a letter to the new Khan of Khiva, Arab Muhammad Khan II (1702-1704). The following comments were made about this letter in the Moscow journal in April 1704: “The Khan of Khiva sent a letter to our supreme emperor through his group of ambassadors. In this letter, the Khan of Khiva expressed his loyalty to His Highness along with all his possessions. His Highness graciously accepted this offer and sent his ambassadors to the Khan of Khiva” [2:538, 539]. Such letters were written in the middle of the 18th century during the reign of the puppet khan Nurali (1741-1742), who was brought from the Kazakh tribes to Khiva. Nuralikhan was the son of the Kazakh Khan Abul Khayr Khan, and according to Russian voyager Valikhonov, after 1740, the Khivan people appointed a Khan from the Kazakhs, who were officially considered Russian citizens. It is known that Kazakh Khan Abul Khayr Khan became a Russian citizen in 1731 through the Russian ambassador Murza Tevkele who came to the Kazakh state of Little Juz [1:37].

At the end of the 18th and 19th centuries, the relations between Russia and the Khiva Khanate grew somewhat. This was influenced by the development of the textile industry in Russia and the demand for raw materials. However, the tsar's government consistently continued its plan to invade Central Asia. For example, in the 18th century, 46 large and 96 small fortresses were built in the territory of Kazakh lands. 1819 Russian captain N. Muravev came to the Khiva Khanate to negotiate with one of the Bashkird officials. However, this visit failed and he was held captive in Khiva for some time.

In order to realize their interests, the Russian government did not tire of restricting the activities of Uzbek traders. For example, in August 1836, 46 merchants from Khiva were detained while returning from the Nizhny-Novgorod fair. After that, the General-governor of Orenburg sent a letter to Khivan Khan Allah Quli Khan (1825-1842), demanding the release of all Russian prisoners held in Khiva and the elimination of hostility towards the empire. In January of the following year, a messenger came from the Khan of Khiva, saying that he was ready to release the Russian prisoners if he freed the captured merchants and demolished the fortress of Novo-Alexandrovsk, which was built on the shore of the Caspian Sea. In November 1837, the ambassador from the Khiva Khanate, Kabulboy, came to Russia. According to sources, he brought 25 Russian prisoners with him. But, the Russians were dissatisfied with this and sent a new ambassador to Khiva. According to Valikhanov, 100 Russian prisoners were released after two years. However, in 1839, about 200 Russian fishermen were captured again by the Khivan turkmens on the shores of the Caspian Sea [2:547, 548]. For this reason, on November 26, 1839, the tsar's government issued an order to organize a military expedition against Khiva. Captain (later General) Perovsky was appointed as its commander and provided with 5,000 soldiers and everything for a military expedition. However, this expedition was forced to turn back due to the attack of Turkmen, Kazakh, and Uzbek tribes on the way and bad weather. In 1840, the Minister of Military, Count Chernyshev, sent a special letter to Perovsky, ordering him to prepare for a new campaign. However, by the order of the tsar on May 19 of 1840, this march was postponed [1:43].

Khivan Khan Allah Quli Khan sent an ambassador to Istanbul after hearing the news about the new Russian attack. After receiving no response from Istanbul, British ambassadors Abbot and Shakespeare arrived, met with the Khan and recommended to release all Russian prisoners in order not to leave an excuse for a new war with Russia. After the danger was eliminated, the Khan informed the Turks by sending an ambassador named Qutb al-din Khoja to Istanbul. Later, he sent an ambassador to the British to express his gratitude [1:54].

In 1841, another ambassador, Captain Nikoforov, was sent from Russia to Khiva. His main task was not only to meet and negotiate with the khan, but also to cut Khiva's influence on Kazakhs who are Russian citizens and to persuade the khan to stay neutral on the issue of Russian occupation of the lower Syr Darya region. But, he could not fulfill this task. A year later, on December 27, 1842, another Russian ambassador G. Danilevsky came to Khiva and managed to sign a document called “Act of Obligations” to Khan of Khiva Rahim Quli Khan (1842-1846). According to the act, the khan was obliged to improve his relations with Russia and give great privileges to Russian

merchants. This has led to increased trade relations between Russia and Khiva. Because, according to the contract, the khan gave Russian merchants equal rights with local merchants, did not increase the trade tax by 5%, and allowed merchants to move from the Khiva region to other countries. Since 1858, the volume of trade duty has been reduced to 2.5% [3:10].

In the subsequent diplomatic relations, the interests of Russia were mainly pursued and, as much as possible, they sought to make Central Asia economically dependent on the empire. Because during this period, the Russian light industry developed rapidly, but there was a shortage of cotton due to the civil war in America. As an example, it can be shown that in 1860, the volume of cotton import to Russia from the Central Asian countries was 174,059 poods (a unit of weight around 16.38 kg), and in 1864 it had reached 459,391 poods. The Khanates of Central Asia imported from Russia increased from 22% to 42% during 1862-1867.

In 1858, the diplomatic group headed by Colonel N. Ignatev sent to Khiva became extremely important for Russia. Because this group of ambassadors acted as a spy for Russia. among their tasks was to collect as much information as possible about the deserts of Khiva and Bukhara, to determine the relations of these two countries with the Kazakhs, Turkmens and Karakalpaks, to find traces of the Amu Darya basin and its old basins, and thereby verify the maps drawn earlier.

On the eve of the marches to the Central Asia, trade links with Khiva expanded even more. Because during this period, due to the military operations with Kokand and Bukhara, the main trade relations were conducted with this country. For this reason, Russian exports to Bukhara decreased from 4,655,000 rubles to 877,000 rubles during 1864-1866, while the volume of trade with Khiva increased from 11,000 rubles to 1,565,000 rubles. But, during the military operations against the Khiva Khanate, this indicator decreased again to 2/3 [3:51].

During this period, relations between the two countries were destroyed by Kazakh bandits in the Kazakh deserts. For this reason, in the letter of Turkestan Governor-General von Kaufman on November 19, 1867, he proposed to open a new trade route from Krasnovodsk to Khiva. During this period, trade relations between Russia and Khiva were mainly in 2 directions: 1. 65-day journey from Khiva to Orenburg through Kazakh deserts (33 days according to some sources [4:78]). 2. Roads from Khiva to Astrakhan through Mangyshlak were used. The road from Krasnovodsk to Khiva took 12-17 days. This path was convenient for Russia in every way. Because, firstly, Krasnovodsk was connected with the central cities of Russia through the strait and sea, secondly, it served to keep the Turkmen tribes under control, thirdly, it served as a ground for future military campaigns, and fourthly, it served to cut off the influence of the British on Central Asia, which divides them from the south.

However, according to some sources, this proposal was made earlier by N. who came to Khiva in 1819. He was invited by Muravev to the Khan. In that meeting, N. After Muravev presented his gifts to Khan, the next day there was an official reception. Khoja Mahram and Yusuf Mehtar, officials, took part in it along with the Khan. After a diplomatic proposal, the ambassador suggested the development of trade relations through this route, which was proposed by the commander-in-chief of the Caucasus Army A.P. Yermolov. However, the Khan rejects his proposal [4:78].

However, according to some sources, N. Muravev, who came to Khiva in 1819, proposed this proposal to the khan. At that meeting, after N. Muravev presented his gifts to Khan, there was an official reception the next day. Khoja Mahram and Yusuf Mehtar, officials, took part in it along with the Khan. After a diplomatic proposal, the ambassador suggested the development of trade relations through this route, which was proposed by the commander-in-chief of the Caucasus Army A.P. Yermolov. However, the Khan rejects his proposal [4:78].

In 1871, the government of Khiva sent ambassadors to Tbilisi and Petersburg to protest von Kaufman's actions, but in January of this year, an order was issued to prepare for military operations against Khiva. For this reason, in 1872, Khivan Khan sent his ambassadors to Calcutta to ask for help from the English Lord Northburgh. When this did not work, Khiva began to independently prepare for the upcoming war.

The main military operations against the Khiva Khanate began in May 1873 and ended on August 12 of this year with the conclusion of the “Gandumyan” treaty. After this agreement, a number of changes took place in the administrative, political, and economic life of the Khiva Khanate. In particular, the lands belonging to the Khiva Khanate on the right bank of the Amu Darya River were handed over to Russia. Here, the Amu Darya department of the Syr Darya region was established, and the Khivan Khan was practically subordinated to the head of the department. Almost all of Khan’s foreign, military and financial affairs were carried out with the advice of the head of the Amu Darya department. This caused territorial problems after the war. There were several disputes between the head of the Amu Darya department and the Khivan Khan on this issue. For example, in volume 1 of the documents of Khiva khans kept in the Central State Archive of Uzbekistan, on October 24, 1874, the head of the Amu Darya Department, Ivanov, wrote to the khan in a letter asking him to send a representative to clearly define the borders. Also, in this volume, in a letter written on July 2, 1874, information was given about the Karakalpaks living along the Taliq and Ulkan rivers [5 1:4-8].

In addition, according to the contract, Khiva undertook to pay a contribution to Russia in the amount of 2,200,000 rubles for 20 years. After the customs reform of 1885, Khanate markets were filled with Russian goods. Although the Khivans managed to increase their income from trade with Russia during this period, most of the income was used to pay the contract money. However, after 1881, the annual contribution was increased to 200,000 rubles. This contract money was paid in full only by 1893. It should be said that a certain part of this contribution was imposed on the Turkmen tribes living in Khiva Khanate. During the study of the archive documents of the Khans of Khiva, in the letter written by Colonel Ivanov, the head of the Amudar department at that time, to the Khan, the contributions of the Turkmens to the tribes of Imrali, Chawdoor, Karayulgun, Ala Eli, Yawmoot, Karadash were brought in Khivan gold puls and Russian rubles, and the unpaid parts were clearly indicated [5 20 :4]. During this period, Muhammad Rahim Khan II (1864-1910) almost lost his foreign and military powers, but he aspired to a little internal independence. The Russian government appointed the Khan to various positions and awarded him with various awards to keep him on track. For example, on August 16, 1908, in a telegram sent by the head of the Amudar department, Glushanovsky, it is written: “...His Highness The Great emperor awarded you on August 12 with the medal of St. Vladimir, I degree. I am sending this to you through my coadjutor Moses” [5 274:2].

Khan also had to send letters of friendship to the leaders of the Russian government. In particular, the following points were expressed in the letter of the khan to Lieutenant-General Ivanov, who was appointed as the new Governor-General of Turkestan: “His Majesty and His Highness the Emperor bestowed upon us and our crown son Asfandiyar on December 21, 1902, and always look upon us with confidence. For this reason, we intend to render our sincere service to His Highness the Great Emperor...” [5 110:2].

Another letter contains the list of ambassadors of Khivan Khan which sent to congratulate on this occasion. This ambassadors group had included, Asfandiyar Tura (the head of the group of ambassadors), Captain Muhammad Husaynbek son of Muhammad Murad divanbegi, the Governor of Imrali Sardarbay son of Muhammad Murad divanbegi, the Governor of Khanqo governor Aminbay son of Ismailbay, translator and consultant Kornilov, a merchant Muhammad Vafabay son of Baqqal, and another mahram[5 110:20].

In conclusion, although the diplomatic relations between Khiva and Russia were equal in the early days, the Russian emperors constantly tried to subjugate this country and sent a group of spies who undertook to perform special tasks in the guise of each of their ambassadors. In the end, due to the collected information, they managed to completely occupy this country. Khans of Khiva often sought economic benefits from these relations.

Referance

1. Туркистон Чор Россияси мустамлакачилиги даврида. – Тошкент; Шарқ, 2000. (Turkestan during the colonial period of Tsarist Russia. – Tashkent; Sharq, 2000)
2. Valikhanov, M.Veniukof. Russian in Central Asia. – London, 1865.
3. Saymour Becker. Russia’s protectorats in Central Asia (Bukhara and Khiva, 1865-1924). – New York, 2005.
4. Grant report “History of the Khanate of Khiva from the 16th century to 1920”.Khorezm Mamun academy. –Khiva, 2005.
5. Materials of “Archive Document Fund of Khans of Khiva”. Central State Archive of Uzbekistan. The Fund of I-125.

boshlab, ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetensiyani shakllantirish, ijtimoiy munosabatlar madaniyatini rivojlantirish, refleksiv-metagnitiv o'sish va dunyoqarash transformatsiyasigacha bo'lgan izchil jarayonni qamrab oladi.

Birinchi bosqich – qadriyatlarni anglash va o'zlashtirish. Bu bosqichda talaba ma'naviy-axloqiy tushunchalarni shaxsiy hayot va kasbiy faoliyat uchun muhim tamoyillar sifatida qabul qiladi. Halollik, adolat, shukronalik, vafodorlik, mehribonlik, kamtarlik va sabr kabi sifatlarning mazmunini anglash talabning keyingi rivojlanishi uchun poydevor bo'ladi. Agar qadriyatlar ongli ravishda o'zlashtirilmasa, ular xulq-atvorda barqaror namoyon bo'lmaydi. Shu sababli modelda qadriyatlarga oid muloqot, hikmatlar tahlili, badiiy-pedagogik matnlar, tarixiy misollar va refleksiv savollar muhim vosita sifatida qo'llanadi.

Ikkinchi bosqich – ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetensiyani shakllantirish. Bu bosqichda qadriyatlar amaliy ko'nikma va xulq-atvor sifatida namoyon bo'la boshlaydi. Talaba axloqiy vaziyatlarda qaror qabul qiladi, o'z fikrini asoslaydi, boshqalarning nuqtayi nazarini hurmat qiladi, adolati muloqotga kirishadi va o'z harakatining oqibatini baholaydi. Mazkur kompetensiya pedagogik kasb uchun ayniqsa muhim, chunki o'qituvchi o'z shaxsiy namunasi orqali o'quvchilarga ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Uchinchi bosqich – ijtimoiy munosabatlar madaniyatini rivojlantirish. Najmiddin Kubro merosida insonning kamoloti jamiyat bilan aloqadorlikda namoyon bo'ladi. Shaxsning ichki pokligi uning boshqalarga bo'lgan munosabatida, muloqot odobida, hamkorlikda, insonparvarlikda va fuqarolik mas'uliyatida ko'rinadi. Shu sababli talabalarda ijtimoiy-kommunikativ sifatlarni rivojlantirish ma'naviy tarbiyaning muhim ko'rsatkichi hisoblanadi.

To'rtinchi bosqich – refleksiv-metagnitiv rivojlanishni faollashtirish. Bu bosqichda talaba o'z xatosini ko'ra olish, uni tan olish, tuzatish, kelgusi rivojlanish maqsadini belgilash va o'z ustida ishlash ko'nikmalariga ega bo'ladi. Najmiddin Kubro ta'limotidagi tavba va o'zini tahlil qilish g'oyalari aynan shu bosqichning nazariy asosini tashkil etadi. Pedagogik amaliyotda bu bosqich portfoliolar, o'z-o'zini baholash varaqalari, refleksiv esselar va individual rivojlanish xaritalari orqali qo'llab-quvvatlanadi.

Beshinchi bosqich – dunyoqarash transformatsiyasi va komil inson idealiga yaqinlashish. Bu bosqichda talaba bilim, qadriyat, tajriba, refleksiya va ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni yagona hayotiy pozitsiyaga birlashtiradi. Komil inson ideali zamonaviy pedagogik ta'limda axloqiy mas'uliyatli, kasbiy kompetent, insonparvar, ijtimoiy faol va o'z ustida ishlaydigan shaxsni tarbiyalash maqsadi bilan uyg'unlashadi.

2-jadval. Ma'naviy rivojlanish blokida shakllantiriladigan ijobiy sifatlar va ularning salbiy muqobillari

Ijobiy sifat	Pedagogik mazmuni	Salbiy sifat	Tarbiyaviy xavf
Halollik	Rostgo'ylik, vijdonlilik va haqiqatga sodiqlik.	Yolg'onchilik	Ishonchning yo'qolishi va axloqiy beqarorlik.
Mas'uliyat	Vazifa va burchni ongli bajarish.	Mas'uliyatsizlik	Burchga loqaydlik, kasbiy sustlik.
Insonparvarlik	Boshqalarga hurmat, mehr va yordamga tayyorlik.	Shafqatsizlik	Inson manfaatiga befarqlik.
Kamtarlik	O'zini yuqori qo'yimaslik, oddiylik.	Kibr	Boshqalarni mensimaslik.
Sabr-toqat	Qiyinchilikni matonat bilan yengish.	Sabrsizlik	Shoshqaloqlik, hissiy beqarorlik.
Bag'rikenglik	Turli fikr va qarashlarni hurmat qilish.	Murosasizlik	Nizo va inkor kayfiyati.
O'zini nazorat qilish	Nafs, hissiyot va xatti-harakatni boshqarish.	Nafsga berilish	Hirs va impulsiv qarorlar.
Ilmga intilish	Bilim olish va o'zini rivojlantirishga ehtiyoj.	Johillik	O'rganishga befarqlik.